

Central Asian Journal of STEM

TEACHERS' ROLE IN ADDRESSING DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOUR IN UNIVERSITY

Nurbek Khamzayev

Kimyo International University in Tashkent, Student

Supervisor: Tolibjon Yuldoshev

e-mail: uralji03@gmail.com; +998932221454

Abstract: Disruptive behaviour in a foreign language classroom can have a negative impact on student learning and engagement; thus, a teacher's role is important in preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour [1]. This research investigates the role of the teachers at Kimyo International University in Tashkent in preventing and responding to the disruptive behaviour of students. The study used surveys and classroom observations to gather data, involving 11 English language instructors from Kimyo International University in Tashkent. Additionally, 3 lessons were observed. The findings demonstrate that teachers play a key role in preventing disruptive behaviour by establishing clear expectations for behaviour, creating a positive and supportive learning environment, and building rapport with students. Teachers can also respond to disruptive behaviour effectively by using various strategies, such as redirecting students, providing positive reinforcement, and using assertive discipline techniques. The study concludes that teachers can play a significant role in creating a positive and productive learning environment by effectively preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour.

Keywords: disruptive behaviour, linguistic frustrations, cultural misunderstandings, teacher-student rapport, culturally sensitive approach, conducive learning atmosphere, classroom dynamics

1. Introduction

In a diverse university foreign language class, where different cultures and languages come together, disruptions can occur as unexpected problems, affecting the beauty of the language learning process. Balancing class discipline while dealing with the complexities of a new language is a significant challenge for teachers, going beyond typical classroom management issues [2]. These disruptions, often rooted in linguistic frustrations, cultural misunderstandings, and the anxiety of mastering a foreign tongue, can deter the learning process if not adequately addressed. This study explores the pivotal role teachers play in preventing and addressing these interruptions. Through a mixed-method approach encompassing classroom observations, interviews with seasoned language instructors, and surveys from students across diverse language classes, the research was delved into the strategies employed by educators in real-time. The results highlight the multifaceted strategies teachers use and mention the importance of a proactive and culturally sensitive approach. As this study reveals, effective foreign language instruction hinges not only on linguistic expertise but equally on adept classroom management tailored to the unique challenges of the language-learning environment.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The nature and causes of disruptive behaviour

According to Emre Debreli and Inara Ishanova [3], it is widely accepted that effective classroom management enhances students' learning experiences. While simply controlling the classroom does not guarantee improved learning results, the bond formed between the teacher and students promotes joint understanding of their responsibilities, fostering a more conducive learning atmosphere. Wolfgang and Glickman [4] also emphasised the same point, stressing the importance of teachers building relationships with students and creating a supportive learning environment. This can be achieved by the way teachers oversee the classroom, including implementing systems of rules, rewards, or consequences. Regarding the fundamental reasons for misbehaviour, several factors contribute to this phenomenon in educational settings, from primary to higher education. These include cultural differences, low student motivation, large class sizes, time constraints, and students dealing with personal or family issues [5], [6]. Elias and Schwab stated that classroom disruptions often stem from certain causes and manifest in behaviours teachers commonly perceive as misbehaviour [7]. Examples of such behaviours include using phones, wearing headphones, creating non-verbal disturbances, being tardy, and not focusing during lessons.

Professors Robert Dobmeier and Joseph Moran have developed a framework to understand disruptive behaviours among adult learners [2]. This structure categorises behaviour into three distinct levels: inattentive, acting out, and threatening/harmful/violent. Additionally, they identified four variables that play a significant role in triggering these disruptive behaviours. This comprehensive framework offers a deeper insight into the challenges educators face when managing adult learners.

Given the complexities of classroom dynamics and the varied reasons for disruptions, it's crucial for educators to be equipped with both an understanding of the underlying causes and effective strategies. The insights from various experts highlight the necessity for a proactive, informed approach to classroom management, ensuring a conducive environment for learners.

2.2 Preventing disruptive behaviour: The role of the teacher

Aamer Sohail (2023) mentions: "Teachers play a pivotal role not only in imparting knowledge but also in creating an environment conducive to learning" [8]. In a classroom environment, the teacher (often paralleled by the manager in a workplace setting) plays a crucial role in shaping the atmosphere and dynamics of the space [9]. Siti Khasinah [1] underlines that the foundational premise across these expert viewpoints emphasises the importance of fostering a positive classroom environment to mitigate disruptive behaviours. Firstly, building strong teacher-student relationships is foundational. When students feel seen, heard, and valued, they are more likely to be invested in the learning process and less likely to exhibit disruptive behaviour (Brown, 2001) [10]. Brown advocates for establishing rapport, balancing affirmations with constructive feedback, and cultivating an energetic learning ambiance. Building this rapport entails valuing each student's individuality, seeking their input, and sharing in their achievements. Establishing rapport from the onset, getting to know students individually, understanding their backgrounds and unique challenges, and displaying genuine care and interest can foster a sense of belonging and purpose. This foundation makes students more receptive to feedback and guidance.

Structuring the classroom environment effectively is another preventative measure. According to Andrea Banks [11], "Clear and consistent expectations about behaviour should be set and reinforced regularly". She suggests to keep your students interested and involved, combine the following positive reinforcement techniques: "Nonverbal cues (thumbs up, jazz hands, clapping), Verbal praise ("thank you for participating," "excellent question"), Tangible rewards (bite-sized candies for class participation), Activity rewards (five minutes of free time for those who stay on task), Group rewards (end of the month pizza party for no tardies)". Moreover, engaging lesson plans that cater to diverse learning styles can reduce disruptions arising out of boredom or frustration. Utilizing hands-on activities, group discussions, multimedia resources, and real-life applications can capture students' attention and interest (Jane Higgins, 2023) [12]. Effective classroom management strategies are also essential. Team Varthana (2023) informs that celebrating achievements, providing positive feedback, and offering rewards can motivate students to adhere to classroom norms. Conversely, having a clear system of consequences, applied fairly and consistently, deters disruptive behaviour [13]. It's essential that these consequences are not punitive but corrective, aiming to teach rather than punish [13].

Moreover, the experiential aspect of learning plays a role in sustaining this positive energy across lessons. Charles [14] and Marsh [15] spotlight the significance of effective interpersonal skills, with a three-tiered focus on general relationship-building, student-specific interactions, and fostering communication with parents. They champion a holistic approach centred on open communication, warmth, and consistent support to foster a thriving classroom atmosphere. In addition, Emre Debreli and Inara Ishanova [3] compiled several approaches that have been suggested to address behavioural challenges in the classroom. These include providing precise instructions and overseeing students [16], engaging students with tasks and responsibilities [17], clearly defining rules and their repercussions [18], and diversifying classroom activities [19].

2.3 Responding to Disruptive Behaviour

Scholars such as Khasinah suggest that addressing disruptive behaviours promptly and efficiently is important, as unchecked disruptions can compromise all classroom members [1]. Nyitray (2012) stated, "In order

to promote a respectful and polite campus climate, it's critical to set clear expectations, promote dialogue, and provide constant support for issues [20]. When educators make it obvious how important it is for students to behave respectfully in the classroom, they find that it helps to reduce behavioural issues with their students." The first thing to do is stay calm and think before reacting. The website "The University of Washington" (n.d.) outlined several strategies to deal with disruptive students, such as: "Be steady, consistent, and firm," "Give the person's sentiments your acknowledgment," "Recall that tension or irritation is frequently the root cause of disruptive behaviour," "Respond to each disturbance personally, clearly, and right away," "Describe disruptive behaviour in detail and establish boundaries," "If the student disobeys you, take them out of that particular class period," "After requesting that the student leave, you can call UWPD for assistance if they refuse," "To address the disruption, investigate the reasons behind the incident and talk about appropriate behaviour, ask the student to come to see you after class," "Keep an eye out for indicators that the situation is about to turn violent" [21].

3. Methodology

This research delves into "The role of the teacher in preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour in the foreign language classroom at universities", to comprehensively explore this topic, a mixed-methods research design was employed, incorporating classroom observations of English Education faculties and a survey to question teachers of English language classes of Kimyo International University in Tashkent. This section outlines the methodology adopted for this study. The mixed-methods approach combined both qualitative and quantitative methods. This combination allows for an understanding of the role of teachers in managing disruptive behaviour in foreign language classrooms.

3.1 Observation

For the observational component, first, second, and third-year students were selected from the English Education faculty. The purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure diversity in class profiles, teaching methods, and student demographics. These observations were conducted in classrooms with an average student enrolment of about 16-20. Each observation session spanned the entire class period, during which detailed field notes were taken. The observations were primarily focused on identifying disruptive behaviour, evaluating teacher responses, and assessing the overall classroom dynamics. After that, a qualitative analysis was performed on the information gathered from the classroom observations. To find common themes about disruptive behaviour, teacher reactions, and classroom dynamics, thematic analysis was employed. By employing a systematic approach, a comprehensive understanding of the role of teachers in managing disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms was achieved.

3.2 Survey

The online survey was made using Google Forms and distributed to teachers from the English language and English Education departments of Kimyo International University in Tashkent. A convenience sample of 11 teachers responded to the survey, providing valuable insights into their experiences and strategies for managing disruptive behaviour. The survey consisted of 12 closed-ended questions. It collected information about the common average number of students in lessons; the frequency and types of disruptive behaviour encountered; the strategies and techniques employed by teachers, and their demographic details. Respondents completed the survey at their convenience. The website Google Forms demonstrated and analysed automatically the received data. The findings were scrutinised to draw meaningful conclusions.

4. Data Collection and Analysis

Entering the Data Collection and Analysis phase, the research focuses on the empirical investigation into the teacher's role in managing disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms. The observational data, derived from observing three class contexts, forms the basis for evaluating the intricate interplay between lesson preparation, disruptive incidents, teaching strategies, and responses. Complementing this, insights gathered from survey responses of 11 experienced language educators provide an additional layer of perspectives.

4.1 Classroom observation

Three observations were conducted at Kimyo International University in Tashkent to examine classroom dynamics and teacher-student interactions. The first observation, labelled "Observation A," took place on 24.10.2023 during a Classroom Management lesson. For this observation, a third-year classroom with 16 participants was selected, showcasing a positive atmosphere influenced by the teacher's welcoming demeanour. The teacher effectively managed disruptions through proactive engagement strategies, utilising handouts and interactive materials that seamlessly aligned with the lesson's topic.

Moving on to the second observation, conducted on 25.10.2023 during a Grammar Vocabulary class and named "Observation B." A first-year class of 17 students was chosen, and the teacher's approach fostered a balanced and friendly atmosphere. By rearranging the classroom layout and incorporating engaging activities such as the "Mafia" game, the teacher encouraged healthy competition. Identified causes of disruptive behaviour included language comprehension issues, lateness, and side conversations. The teacher addressed these issues through teaching strategies such as explanation, revision, and individualised feedback, effectively managing disruptions proactively.

Finally, in "Observation C" on 26.10.2023, researchers observed a lesson on "Modern Teaching Methods" for second-year students with 15 participants. The teacher's collaborative and approachable manner created an atmosphere of curiosity and mutual respect. A dynamic lesson plan incorporating modern teaching methods contributed to the success of the class. Disruptive behaviour, including device use and side conversations, was addressed by integrating technology into the lesson and redirecting attention through interactive online quizzes. The teacher played the role of a facilitator, promoting student-centred learning.

4.2 Teacher questionnaire: "Survey"

Commencing the analysis of the survey responses, the investigation delves into the perspectives of 11 experienced language educators regarding disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms. The data shows that 90.9% of teachers responded that they commonly have 15-30 students in a lesson, while 9.1% might have 31-50 students (See picture 6). In examining the responses to the question on the significance of the classroom environment in fostering effective learning, it is evident that the majority of the participants, constituting 72.7%, indicated that it is "very important" (See picture 7). The results of the question regarding the frequency of encountering disruptive behaviour in lessons show a diverse pattern emerged among the 11 participants. The majority, comprising 54.5% of respondents, selected "Sometimes". A smaller proportion, accounting for 9.1%, chose "Rarely" suggesting infrequent disruptions in the learning environment. On the other hand, 27.3% of participants acknowledged encountering disruptive behaviour "Often". Notably, 9.1% of respondents selected "Always" (See picture 1). To the question "Which of the following disruptive behaviours are most common in your classroom?" a nuanced pattern emerges among the 11 participants. A notable portion, representing 54.5%, identified "Talking out of turn" as a common disruptive behaviour. The majority, constituting 90.9% of participants, pointed to the frequent occurrence of "Using electronic devices without permission."

How often do you encounter disruptive behavior in lessons?
11 responses

Picture 1.

Additionally, 63.6% of respondents acknowledged "Arriving late" as disruptive behaviour, reflecting its significant presence in the classroom environment. Meanwhile, a smaller but distinct group, comprising 27.3%, cited "Refusing to participate" as a disruptive behaviour (See picture 2). The establishment of classroom norms and

Which of the following disruptive behaviors is most common in your classroom?
11 responses

expectations at the beginning of a course. A notable majority, constituting 54.5%, consistently affirmed that they "Always" set clear classroom norms and expectations.

Picture 2.

Furthermore, 36.4% of respondents indicated that they do so "Often." A smaller proportion, representing 9.1%, reported doing this "Sometimes" (See picture 8). Additionally, analysing responses about techniques for preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour 54.5% endorsed the approach of "Setting clear classroom rules and expectations at the start," while a close 45.5% opted for the alternative strategy of "Engaging students with interactive and hands-on activities" (See picture 9). The question on involving students in setting classroom rules demonstrated that 45.5% indicated "Sometimes," while a combined 36.4% chose less frequent involvement, with 18.2% selecting "Rarely" and 18.2% choosing "Never." Conversely, a smaller but notable 9.1% reported "Always" involving students, and a similar percentage of 9.1% chose "Often" (See picture 3). The significance of understanding different cultures to prevent problems in the classroom was also included in the survey. A substantial 54.5% of respondents deemed cultural understanding as "Very Essential" while 36.4% considered it "Essential".

Do you involve students in the process of setting classroom rules?

11 responses

Picture 3

A singular participant, constituting 9.1%, expressed a neutral stance on the matter (See picture 4). Furthermore, in the responses to the frequency of using non-verbal interventions to address disruptions, a consistent trend emerged among the 11 participants. The majority, constituting 63.6%, reported using these interventions "Often" while a notable 36.4% indicated doing so "Always" (See picture 10). The preferred focus when addressing disruptive behaviour showed that 81.8% chose "Both equally" and reported that they "Often" focus on both the individual student and the behaviour. Conversely, a minority, representing 18.2%, of participants selected "The behaviour" (See picture 11). Finally, assessing opinions on the impact of disruptive behaviour on overall learning outcomes, the majority of respondents, constituting 81.8%, "Agree" that disruptive behaviour significantly affects the course outcomes, with 36.4% expressing a "Strongly agree" sentiment. In contrast, a smaller but notable portion, comprising 18.2%, expressed a "Neutral" stance (See picture 5).

How important is understanding different cultures to help prevent problems in the classroom?

11 responses

Picture 4

Picture 5

5. Results

In the results, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the teacher's role in preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms. The three classroom observations at Kimyo International University revealed diverse strategies employed by teachers. "Observation A" underscored the efficacy of proactive engagement strategies in a third-year Classroom Management lesson, creating a positive atmosphere. In "Observation B," the first-year Grammar Vocabulary class showcased the teacher's adept management of disruptive behaviours, addressing issues like language comprehension and lateness through

In your opinion, does disruptive behavior significantly impact the overall learning outcomes of a course?
11 responses

strategic teaching methods. "Observation C" demonstrated the integration of technology and collaborative teaching methods in a second-year "Modern Teaching Methods" class, effectively managing disruptive behaviours linked to device use and side conversations.

The survey data presents a comprehensive view of the perspectives of 11 experienced language educators on disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms. The high percentage (90.9%) of teachers commonly having 15-30 students suggests a prevailing class size norm, potentially influenced by institutional policies or practical considerations. The emphasis made by 72.7% of instructors who have chosen the variant "very important" role of the classroom environment in fostering effective learning underscores the shared belief in the significant impact of the learning space on student engagement and outcomes. The diverse pattern in responses to the frequency of encountering disruptive behaviour (54.5% "Sometimes," 27.3% "Often") could be attributed to variations in teaching contexts, student demographics, or pedagogical approaches of instructors.

Regarding common disruptive behaviours in the classes, the identification of "Talking out of turn" by 54.5% and the prevalence of "Using electronic devices without permission" noted by 90.9% highlight issues linked to classroom participation and technology use. The acknowledgment of "Arriving late" by 63.6% of teachers underscores its substantial presence, while the smaller group citing "Refusing to participate" (27.3%) suggests a multifaceted nature of disruptive behaviours, possibly influenced by diverse student attitudes or learning preferences.

The majority of educators (54.5%) affirming that they always set clear classroom norms and expectations at the beginning of a course signals a proactive approach to behaviour management. Furthermore, the preference for "Setting clear classroom rules and expectations" (54.5%) and the alternative strategy of "Engaging students with interactive and hands-on activities" (45.5%) reflects a balanced perspective on preventing disruptive behaviour, catering to varied teaching styles. In terms of student involvement in setting rules, the responses indicate a spectrum of practices, from frequent involvement ("Sometimes" – 45.5% and "Often" – 9.1%) to less frequent participation ("Rarely" – 18.2% and "Never" – 18.2%). This variation could stem from differing pedagogical philosophies or institutional expectations. The significance of cultural understanding, as deemed "Very Essential" by 54.5%, and "Essential" by 36.4%, underlines the importance of a culturally responsive approach in managing disruptive behaviour.

The consistent trend in using non-verbal interventions ("Often" – 63.6%, "Always" – 36.4%) indicates a shared strategy among educators, possibly driven by its effectiveness in maintaining a positive classroom atmosphere. The majority (81.8%) focusing "Both equally" on the individual student and behaviour when addressing disruptive behaviour reflects a comprehensive approach to classroom management, while the minority (18.2%) solely focusing on "The behaviour" may prioritise broader strategies.

The widespread agreement (81.8%) on the significant impact of disruptive behaviour on course outcomes, with a considerable portion (36.4%) expressing a "Strongly agree" sentiment, underscores the collective recognition of the disruptive behaviour's potential to influence overall learning effectiveness. The smaller but notable group (18.2%) expressing a "Neutral" stance may suggest varying interpretations of the disruptive

behaviour's impact, warranting further investigation into nuanced perspectives. Overall, the survey data provides a rich foundation for understanding the nuanced approaches and perspectives of language educators in addressing disruptive behaviour in the university foreign language classroom.

6. Conclusion and Further Implications

In conclusion, this research illuminates the important role of teachers in preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour in university foreign language classrooms. The study reveals a complex interplay of factors influencing classroom dynamics, ranging from class size norms and the significance of the learning environment to the multifaceted nature of disruptive behaviours. Teachers, as highlighted through classroom observations and survey responses, employ diverse strategies such as proactive engagement, technology integration, and clear establishment of classroom norms to effectively manage disruptions. The emphasis on cultural understanding, the use of non-verbal interventions, and the comprehensive approach to addressing disruptive behaviour underscore the multifaceted nature of the teacher's role in creating a conducive learning atmosphere.

Further implications of this research extend to the ongoing development of strategies and interventions to enhance classroom management. The findings suggest a need for continued exploration into the impact of varying class sizes, cultural nuances, and pedagogical approaches on disruptive behaviour. Additionally, future research can delve deeper into the specific challenges posed by different types of disruptive behaviours and involve teachers from various teachers' directions, allowing for the refinement of targeted interventions. The positive correlation between a proactive approach to classroom management and effective learning outcomes calls for continued emphasis on teacher training programs that integrate these strategies. Moreover, investigating the perspectives of students on classroom management practices can provide a holistic understanding of the dynamics at play. As education continues to evolve, this research sets the stage for a nuanced understanding of the teacher's role in fostering an environment conducive to language learning in diverse university settings.

References

1. Khasinah, S. (2017). Managing disruptive behavior of students in language classroom. *Englisia: Journal of Language, Education, and Humanities*, 4(2), 79-89.
2. Dobmeier, R., & Moran, J. (2008). Dealing with disruptive behavior of adult learners. *New horizons in adult education and human resource development*, 22(2), 29-54.
3. Debreli, E., & Ishanova, I. (2019). Foreign language classroom management: Types of student misbehaviour and strategies adapted by the teachers in handling disruptive behaviour. *Cogent Education*, 6(1), 1648629.
4. Wolfgang, C. H., & Glickman, C. (1986). *Solving discipline problems: Strategies for classroom teachers*. Newton, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
5. Baker, J., & Westrup, H. (2000). *The English language teacher's handbook*. London: Continuum.
6. Kayikci, K. (2009). The effect of classroom management skills of elementary school teachers on undesirable discipline behavior of students. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1, 1215–1225.
7. Elias, M. J., & Schwab, Y. (2006). From compliance to responsibility: Social and emotional learning and classroom management. In C. M. Evertson & C. S. Weinstein (Eds.), *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues* (pp. 309–341). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
8. Sohail, A. (2023, September 25). How to Support Students with Anxiety As a teacher. *Educational News in Pakistan*. <https://www.ilmynews.com/2023/09/how-to-support-students-with-anxiety-as.html>
9. Graziano, C. (2005). *School's Out*. *Edutopia*, February/March, 40-44.
10. Brown, H. D. (2001). *Teaching by principles: an interactive approach to language pedagogy*. San Francisco: Longman.
11. Banks, A. (2021, April 13). 5 Activities For Using Positive Reinforcement in the Classroom - Insights to Behavior. *Insights to Behavior*. <https://insightstobehavior.com/blog/5-activities-positive-reinforcement-classroom/>
12. Higgins, J. (2023, March 31). How to Deal with Challenging Behaviour in the Classroom. *CPD Online College*. <https://cpdonline.co.uk/knowledge-base/safeguarding/how-to-deal-with-challenging-behaviour-in-the-classroom/>
13. Team Varthana. (2023, October 12). Importance of classroom reward system in the school. <https://varthana.com/school/why-is-it-important-to-have-a-classroom-reward-system/>
14. Charles, C. M. (2004). *Building classroom discipline* (7th ed.). New York: Longman.
15. Marsh, C. (2008). *Becoming a teacher: knowledge, skills, and issues*. Australia: Pearson.
16. Hastings, R., & Bham, M. (2003). The relationship between student behavior patterns and teacher burnout. *School Psychology International*, 24(1), 56–64. *The Relationship between Student Behaviour Patterns and Teacher Burnout - Richard P. Hastings, Mohammed S. Bham, 2003 (sagepub.com)*

17. Manning, M. L., & Bucher, K. T. (2003). Classroom management: Models, applications, and cases. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill/Prentice Hall.
18. Corzo, J., & Contreras, O. (2011). Understanding and facing discipline-related changes in the English as a foreign language classroom at public schools. *The Nature of Recognition in TEFL Teachers' Lives*, 13(2), 39–51.
19. Labaree, D. (2004). *The trouble with ed schools*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
20. Nyitray, K. J. (2012). *Responding to Disruptions in the Classroom*.
21. University of Washington. (n.d.). Best practices for managing disruptive behavior. <https://dsl.uw.edu/faculty/disruptive-behavior-in-the-classroom/best-practices/>

Appendices

On average, how many students are there in your lessons?

11 responses

Picture 6

How important is the classroom environment in promoting effective learning?

11 responses

Picture 7

Do you set clear classroom norms and expectations at the beginning of a course?

11 responses

Picture 8

What techniques do you use in preventing and responding to disruptive behaviour in the lesson?

11 responses

Picture 9

How often do you use non-verbal interventions (e.g., gestures, eye contact) to address disruptions?

11 responses

Picture 10

When addressing disruptive behavior, do you focus more on:

11 responses

Picture 11

Observation Template

Lesson Subject area: Classroom Management

Date: 24.10.2023

Year Group: third course

Number of students: 16 participants

How did the teacher's manner influence the classroom atmosphere?	The teacher's positive demeanour creates a welcoming and friendly classroom atmosphere, fostering active student engagement and respect. She proactively addresses disruptions, re-engaging disinterested students through questions or attention-seeking strategies. Overall, her effective teaching style promotes a positive and inclusive learning environment, encouraging student participation.
What had the teacher prepared before the lesson and how did it contribute to its success?	The teacher thoughtfully crafted handouts for interactive practice during the lesson. All instructional materials seamlessly aligned with the lesson's topic, capturing the students' attention and encouraging active participation.
The nature and causes of disruptive behaviour?	The nature and causes of disruptive behaviour were evident as some students consistently tended to disrupt the class by engaging in off-topic conversations with their peers. Despite the disruptions, the teacher actively attempted to engage these students, acknowledging the need to address and redirect their attention to the lesson.
What teaching strategies were used? The role of the teacher? (eg: explanation, demonstration, discussion, questioning, etc?)	The teacher employed a multifaceted approach, taking on roles as a facilitator, adviser, and predominantly, a monitor. Throughout the lesson, various teaching strategies were skilfully utilized, including clear explanations to impart knowledge, fostering active student engagement through discussions, and employing effective questioning techniques.
How did the teacher respond to disruptive behaviour?	The teacher promptly addressed disruptive behaviour by knocking on the desk and instructing students to be quiet. With a firm and assertive approach, she effectively managed the disruption and swiftly returned to providing further instructions, ensuring a quick and decisive response to maintain a focused learning environment.

Observation A

Observation Template

Lesson Subject area: Grammar Vocabulary
Date: 25.10.2023
Year Group: first-year
Number of students: 17 participants

How did the teacher's manner influence the classroom atmosphere?	The teacher's approach significantly shaped a classroom atmosphere that balances competitiveness and friendliness. Changing the classroom layout to a circle enhanced collaboration and interaction, creating a dynamic learning environment. The teacher's friendly and positive demeanor also influenced a classroom dynamic marked by healthy competition.
What had the teacher prepared before the lesson and how did it contribute to its success?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teacher used workbooks. 2. She prepared a game "Mafia" with flashcards, etc. All students were active and quiet while playing the game
The nature and causes of disruptive behavior?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not understanding the language. 2. Being late to the lesson (e.g. one of the students came in the middle of the lesson) 3. Talking with mates during the lesson.
What teaching strategies were used? The role of the teacher? (eg: explanation, demonstration, discussion, questioning, etc?)	The teacher used a variety of teaching strategies in the lesson, including explanation, revision, and questioning. These methods were instrumental in facilitating student understanding. The teacher actively engaged with each student by providing individualized feedback on their work. The teacher's role was characterized by a hands-on approach, ensuring that each student received feedback to enhance their learning experience.
How did the teacher respond to disruptive behavior?	The teacher responded proactively to disruptive behavior, addressing incidents promptly with a calm yet firm tone. Instead of reacting with frustration, the teacher refocused the class by reinforcing clear expectations and classroom norms. This consistent approach swiftly resolved disruptions, preserving a positive learning environment.

Observation B

Observation Template

Lesson Subject area: Modern Teaching Methods
Date: 26.10.2023
Year Group: second-year students
Number of students: 15 participants

How did the teacher's manner influence the classroom atmosphere?	The teacher's manner positively influenced the classroom atmosphere by fostering a sense of collaboration and curiosity. Through a friendly and approachable demeanor, the teacher encouraged an open exchange of ideas and made students feel comfortable expressing themselves. This created an atmosphere of mutual respect and active engagement.
What had the teacher prepared before the lesson and how did it contribute to its success?	The teacher prepared a dynamic lesson plan that incorporated various modern teaching methods, including online collaborative platforms, multimedia presentations, and peer-to-peer learning activities. This preparation contributed to the lesson's success by catering to different learning styles and providing an interactive and engaging learning experience.
The nature and causes of disruptive behavior?	Disruptive behavior observed included instances of students using personal devices for non-educational purposes and occasional side conversations. Causes may include distractions from external stimuli, lack of interest, or a need for individualized attention.
What teaching strategies were used? The role of the teacher? (eg: explanation, demonstration, discussion, questioning, etc?)	Teaching strategies involved a combination of interactive discussions, online collaborative activities, and multimedia presentations. The teacher played the role of a facilitator, guiding discussions and encouraging students to explore and share ideas. The emphasis was on student-centered learning, empowering students to take an active role in their language acquisition process.
How did the teacher respond to disruptive behavior?	The teacher responded to disruptive behavior by integrating technology into the lesson. For instance, when noticing students using personal devices for non-educational purposes, the teacher redirected their attention by incorporating a quick interactive online quiz related to the lesson content.

Observation C